

CLINICAL ASPECTS OF COMMUNITY-ACQUIRED PNEUMONIA IN THE ELDERLY**Maşcauţan Alina,***Student, Faculty of General Medicine,
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Republic of Moldova, Chisinau***Abstract**

Community-acquired Pneumonia (CAP) is a widespread disease that mainly affects the elderly, resulting in more serious consequences than among the young population[3]. This increased incidence among the elderly of CAP is due to the fact that physiological changes occur to which the lower respiratory tract is subjected (reduction of mucociliary clearance and cough reflex), the immune system(immunosuppression),but also cormobidities (renal pathology, cardiac,chronic cerebrovascular disease, diabetes mellitus) that occur with the aging of the human body . Among the main causal factors leading to a serious development of CAP among the elderly are alcoholism, tobacco smoking, obesity, various degrees of disability, sedentary lifestyle, bipolar disorder [4].

Keywords: pneumonia, cormobidities, symptoms, elderly

Introducere

At present, the elderly population, older than 65 years, is constantly increasing, but their longevity is not always associated with a satisfactory state of health. A good part of people older than 65 years suffer from a lot concomitant pathologies (two or more chronic pathologies), which leads to an increase in mortalităţii. Pe as the human body ages, changes in the immune system occur, so that most of the elderly are more prone to surrounding infections [1]. Statistical data show that the CAP mortality rate among the elderly remains a dramatic one as it was 1000 years ago , thus reaching some conclusions that by 2050, when 20% of the global population will be elderly, the incidence of community pneumonia will be one of the leading causes of mortality [2].

Aim of the study

Due to the fact that CAP in elderly patients have an atypical clinical picture, diagnosis of pathology occurs late, with severe forms, so we set the goal-to identify the symptoms characteristic of elderly patients with CAP, which requires a specific approach and therapeutic conduct.

Materials and methods

The study included 50 patients diagnosed with community pneumonia, treated in the pulmonology department of IMSP SCM " Sf. Arhanghil Mihail " during the years 2017-2019. More common CAP was found in male gender 35(70%) compared to female gender 15 (30%). The database of the selected materialwas processed statically using the Microsoft Excel program.

Result and discutions

Following the analysis of the 50 elderly patients with CAP , a higher incidence of CAP was observed among patients aged 65-70 years -35(70%), and the lowest frequency occurring in those aged 76-85 years - 5(10%) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Age distribution of elderly patients with CAP

The examination of the anamnesis revealed the presence of comorbidities in elderly patients that may influence the evolution of CAP, or on the contrary may be aggravated following the development of the inflammatory process, which is of great importance in the evolution and prognosis of CAP in elderly patients. It was noted that cardiovascular pathology (Hypertension

-38(76%), chronic heart failure-23(46%), Angina pectoris-22(44%)), is most prevalent in elderly patients with CAP, in second place is located Diabetes Mellitus Type II and pathology of the respiratory system (chronic obstructive Bronchopneumopathy, bronchial asthma) -19 (38%). Table 1.

Table 1.

Cormobidities of elderly patients with CAP

Cormobidities	%
Hypertension	38(76%)
Chronic heart failure	23(46%)
Angina Pectoris	22(44%)
Diabetes Mellitus Type II	19(38%)
Pathologies of the respiratory system	19(38%)
Pathologies of the urinar system	18(36%)
Chronic pancreatitis	8(16%)
Chronic hepatitis	8(16%)
Encephalopathy	5(10%)

In order to highlight the onset of the disease in patients in both groups, the symptoms presented by patients at admission were evaluated.

Table 2.

Clinical manifestations of elderly patients with CAP

Charges	%	
Body temperature values	36,9 °C	14(28%)
	37°C-37,5°C	31(62%)
	37,6 °C-38,5 °C	5(10%)
Shiver	24(48%)	
Chest pain	28(56%)	
Dyspnea	50(100%)	
Headache	14(28%)	
Nausea	5(10%)	
Asthenia	46(92%)	
Sweating	40(80%)	
Altered mental state	8(16%)	
Cough	dry	42(84%)
	wet	8(16%)
General condition	Medium gravity	36(72%)
	Sever gravity	14(28%)
Tachypnea	50(100%)	
Tahycardia	50(100%)	
Peripheral oedema	18(36%)	
Fatigue	45(90%)	

Elderly patients with CAP showed an insidious, atypical onset with a predominance of fatigue, dyspnea, tachypnea, tachycardia, sweating, asthenia. La the majority of elderly patients had subfebrility and only 5 (10%) had fever, due to the presence of multiple cormo-

bidities that patients had (chronic pyelonephritis, urinary infections). Another complaint that elderly people with CAP presented was cough which at 42(84%) was a dry, excruciating one, due to the inability of patients to expectorate. Table 2.

Table3.

Physical examination data in elderly patients with CAP

Features	%	
Submatitia	46(92%)	
Murmur	tightened	39(78%)
	diminished	11(22%)
Small bullous rales	40(80%)	
Crepitations	27(54%)	
Dry rales	15(30%)	

In the physical examination of elderly patients with CAP, we found that in 46(92%) local submatitia, the predominance of the tightened murmur was also revealed 38(78%) compared to the dimunuated one 11(22%).In the auscultatory examination of the thoracic box in elderly patients , the small bullous Rales-40(80%), and the dry ones only at 15 (30%).

Concluzii

1.Clinical onset in most elderly patients is insidious, with a little expressed symptomatology, often with a predominance of general symptoms(general weakness, fatigue, signs of confusion), which contributes to a late establishment of the diagnosis.

2.The evolution of CAP in the elderly is influenced by the presence of cormobidities, which due to the infectious process can decompensate and influence the evolution and prognosis of CAP.

References

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